

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

MW10, an upland variety for rainfed areas

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We evaluated the performance of some new, short-duration rices in 1981 wet season in direct-sown, rainfed upland conditions. MW10 performed well under drought conditions and was

further evaluated in 1982 and 1983.

Yield was very low in 1981 because of severe drought for several consecutive days during booting and dough stage. MW10 yielded an average 3.1 t/ha (see table), 27% more than Sathi, a well-adapted local variety. MW10 had good tillering capacity, high spikelet fertility, and short, bold grains. It matured in 95-100 d. Evaluation is continuing. *ℓ*

Performance of MW10 and other rices in yield trials, Bankura, India.

Variety	Average 1981-83 grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	1000-grain weight (g)
RP1158-90-1	1.9	357	47	21.2
HPU8020	1.8	253	39	14.4
TNAU6464	2.1	340	65	18.8
UPR82-1-7-1-2-1-1	2.5	378	77	18.8
MW10	3.1	408	77	21.0
OR83-23	2.0	355	54	18.0
ADT36	1.8	350	61	15.4
Cauvery	2.1	432	41	17.1
Sathi (local check)	2.2	380	49	22.2

IR50, a stable variety for kar in Thambiraparani tract

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IR50, a short duration, long, slender, white rice variety was introduced recently in Tamil Nadu. IR50, two cultures, and ADT36 were tested at 18 sites in Thambiraparani tract, Tirunelveli District, during kar (Jun-

Sep). Data were analyzed for stability by Eberhart and Russel's (1966) model. IR50 had the highest mean yield (4.2 t/ha), the highest regression coefficient, and mean squared deviation from the regression coefficient nearer zero than three other rices tested (see table). *ℓ*

Yield stability of four rices analyzed by Eberhart and Russel's (1966) model.

Variety or culture	Grain yield (t/ha)	Regression coefficient	Mean square deviation
IR50	4.21	0.7078	0.2197
AS19789	4.08	0.5923	1.596
AS23254	3.67	0.6103	0.9103
ADT36	3.96	0.6508	2.050
CD (P = 0.05) 0.48			

Calpearl, a very high-yielding California japonica rice with desirable indica characteristics

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Before 1981, all short-grained rices released in California had poor physical appearance. Calpearl is the first short-grained variety that has milled grains without white belly or notched kernels and with good translucency. Calpearl was developed from IR1318-16/Earlirose. The F₅ was crossed with Calrose 76.

IR1318-16 was selected from Jin Heung/IR262-43-8-11//Calady and IR262 from Peta/Peta*2//TN1. Its short stature and yield capacity originated from TN1 and the large, translucent kernels from Calady. Jin Heung may be responsible for Calpearl's short grains and Earlirose provided earliness. Calrose 76 has cold tolerance, lodging resistance, and high grain fertility.

Calpearl yields 10 t/ha, about 10% more than the average japonica grown in California and performs well when planted late. Its grains ripen 5 or more days earlier than most japonicas (see table). It can be harvested before the October rainy season, and has 5% lower grain moisture at harvest, which saves fuel during grain drying. Calpearl is easily combine harvested.

Its only disadvantage is that its large translucent kernels closely resemble

Average yield and agronomic characteristics of California rices.

Variety ^a	Tests (no.)	Year	Yield (t/ha)	Moisture at harvest (%)	Days to 50% heading	Plant height (cm)	Percent lodging	Seedling vigor ^b	Hull type ^c
S-201 j	20	1980-84	8.9	19.7	95	89	33	4.2	S
M9 j	20	1980-84	8.4	21.6	93	94	57	4.1	S
M-201 j	20	1980-84	9.4	21.4	94	86	9	4.1	S
Calmochi-202 jg	20	1980-84	8.3	22.2	99	94	28	4.0	S
M-302 j	17	1980-84	9.0	19.9	103	94	24	4.2	S
M-401 j	17	1980-84	9.1	20.0	106	94	52	4.3	S
M7 j	17	1980-84	8.9	21.0	110	97	15	4.4	S
Calrose 76 j	12	1980-84	9.1	18.4	110	97	22	4.3	P
Calpearl j	10	1982-84	9.9	16.3	89	84	20	4.7	P
M-101 j	10	1982-84	8.7	18.7	88	86	43	4.6	S
California Belle i	9	1982-84	7.6	16.9	88	102	42	3.5	S
L-202 i	9	1982-84	9.1	18.5	95	81	3	3.6	S

^aj = japonica, g = glutinous, i = indica. ^b Subjective score: 1 = very poor, 5 = excellent. CS = smooth, P = pubescent.

those of California medium-grain rices. California's Grain Inspection Service has classified Calpearl as a medium-grained variety, but milled Calpearl rice meets

US Department of Agriculture short-grain standards. Calpearl was planted on 24% (32,376 ha) of California riceland in 1983. *ℒ*

ACK-5 for direct seeded rainfed conditions

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ACK-5 was developed from D.6-2-2/IR8 at the College of Agriculture in Kolhapur, India, and released for general cultivation in May 1985.

Performance of ACK-5 in station and adaptive trials, Kolhapur, India.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		
	1983	1984	Average
<i>Station trial</i>			
Direct seeded ^a			
ACK-5	4.7	4.9	4.8
RDN185-2	5.7	4.5	5.1
Transplanted ^b			
ACK-5	5.7	3.3	4.5
RDN185-2	4.1	3.0	3.9
<i>Adaptive trial^c</i>			
Direct seeded			
ACK-5	3.8 (10)	4.0 (14)	3.9
RDN185-2	3.4 (10)	3.4 (14)	3.4
Transplanted			
ACK-5	3.3 (3)	3.0 (23)	3.2
RDN185-2	3.4 (3)	3.0 (23)	3.2

^a Mean of 2 locations. ^b Mean of 3 replications. ^c Numbers in parentheses indicate number of locations.

The semidwarf can be grown direct seeded in rainfed conditions, or transplanted. It matures in 120-125 d when direct seeded and in 110-115 d when transplanted. Grains are short and bold (length: breadth 2.25) without white belly. Cooking quality and taste are acceptable and it has 8.8% crude protein. Recovery is 65% with hulling, 60% with milling, and 54% head rice. Flaked rice is better than that of local varieties.

ACK-5 was evaluated for 8 yr under upland conditions. It yielded

significantly higher than several local varieties. Performance in direct seeded and transplanted station and adaptive trials is compared with that of popular, short-duration RDN185-2 (HS-17/TN1) in the table. ACK-5 yield potential is 4 to 6 t/ha. It yielded 4.9 t/ha in direct-seeded trials in 1984, and 5.7 t/ha in transplanted trials in 1983.

ACK-5 is moderately susceptible to blast but is tolerant of Fe chlorosis and drought stress. It has 20 d seed dormancy. *ℒ*

Katrin: a new rice variety for Tanzania

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IET2397, a strain developed in India, was released as Katrin for general cultivation in Tanzania. A derivative of HR19/2x IR8, Katrin is semidwarf (90 cm), resistant to blast and lodging, photoperiod sensitive, and has medium duration (135 d). Average yield is 5.6 t/ha. Grains are long, slender, and

translucent white with good cooking quality. Amylose content is 30%. Grain length-breadth ratio is 3.43, and volume expansion is 4.2. Fifty percent flowering is achieved in 102 d. It produces about 10 panicles/hill and 1,000-grain wt is 30 g. *ℒ*

CR666, the 60-day rice strains

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CR666 (Sattari/Rasi/Kalinga III) lines